

Knowledge Exchange

Charting New Paths: The Promise of Alternative Publishing Practices

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This study has been commissioned and overseen by Knowledge Exchange (KE), a group of national organisations from six European countries, addressing the challenges of keeping digital research infrastructure and policy aligned with rapid political, technological, and societal changes: CSC in Finland, CNRS in France, DeiC in Denmark, DFG in Germany, Jisc in the UK and SURF in the Netherlands.

Conflict of interest statement

Two of our contributors are associated with alternative publishing platforms. Stephen Pinfield (one of the authors) is an Editor at MetaROR and Alex Freeman (member of the Task & Finish group) is the Creator of Octopus CIC.

Contents

Executive summary	4
<hr/>	
1. Background and Methodology	8
Background and objectives	9
Research design	9
Analytical framework	11
Limitations	11
Supporting publications	11
Research ethics	11
<hr/>	
2. Alternative Publishing Practices and Their Rationale	12
The language of innovation	13
Alternative Publishing Practices	13
Why these practices matter	14
Making progress with limited direct evidence	16
<hr/>	
3. Adoption of Alternative Publishing Practices	20
Within reach	21
Evolution	23
Revolution	24
The influence of support from funders and research performing organisations	25
The implications of unequal rates of adoption	26
<hr/>	
4. The Path Forward	29
Practices over platforms	30
Continuing the transformation	30
Key enablers	32
Long-term implications	34
<hr/>	
References	36
Outputs published via Octopus as part of this project	37
Literature sources	37
<hr/>	
Appendix A: Acknowledgements and participants	40

Executive summary

This work was commissioned by Knowledge Exchange, a group of national organisations from six European countries working to enable open science by supporting information infrastructure at an international level. The project had three goals: to discover how to support innovation in scholarly communication; to gain insights into the maturity and development of alternative publishing platforms; and to develop insights for stakeholders who wish to support or adopt these approaches.

The study consulted 29 participants from across Europe and North America through interviews and focus groups, including researchers, research funding organisations and platform representatives, complemented by a focused literature review and bibliometric analysis.

Definitions and context

The evidence collected pointed to the need to understand alternative publishing practices – the specific things researchers do to share their work – and the systemic barriers that prevent their wider adoption as opposed to platforms. Throughout the research and consultation, six distinct alternative publishing practices emerged: preprint posting, open peer review, preregistration, versioning, review and curation after publication and modular publications. Each addresses specific limitations in conventional publishing workflows, offering benefits around research integrity through transparency; increased speed and efficiency; and shifts in power dynamics towards greater equity and access.

Adoption of alternative publishing practices

The practices examined vary dramatically in their adoption potential. Preprinting and open peer review show promise for short-term increases in uptake, being relatively compatible with existing workflows. Preregistration, versioning and review and curation after publication require evolutionary change, offering clear methodological benefits but demanding significant upfront investment or coordination. Modular publications demand revolutionary transformation, fundamentally reconceptualising how scholarship is structured and shared. The evidence highlights that adoption barriers are systemic rather than technical, as researchers face impossible choices between experimentation and career advancement. This creates a challenge: the innovations promising the greatest systemic benefits are precisely those least adoptable under current incentive structures.

A strategy to enable transformation

Meaningful transformation requires abandoning the false choice between conventional, established venues and alternative platforms. This work suggests that transformation is best understood as a cyclical process in which new practices are developed, tested and progressively embedded within mainstream scholarly communication.

The first phase involves **experimentation and demonstration**, led by research communities, funders and institutions. Alternative publishing practices require dedicated spaces for innovation where they can be tested and refined without forcing researchers to bear

the full career risks of early adoption. These experimental settings enable rapid exploration of new approaches, allow practices to mature through iteration and create proofs of concept that shift expectations within disciplinary communities. Sustaining this experimentation requires recognising it as research and development for scholarly communication, which demands public investment rather than commercial sustainability expectations.

The second phase involves **mainstream adoption**, led by infrastructure and service providers, funders and publishing organisations. Once practices have been tested and their value demonstrated, they can be integrated into infrastructures and platforms that serve researchers at scale. As mainstream infrastructures adopt proven practices and evaluation criteria align, **normalisation and scale** can follow: previously alternative approaches become standard practice, and the cycle begins again as new innovations emerge to address remaining challenges.

Three critical enablers

Success depends on coordinated action across three fronts. Research assessment reform represents the most powerful lever for change: current evaluation criteria create incentives that reward conventional publishing metrics, so reform must move beyond aspirational statements toward concrete changes that recognise alternative publishing practices as markers of transparency and quality. Coordinated stakeholder action must break the current impasse where funders, institutions, disciplines and platforms each wait for others to move first – transformation requires simultaneous intervention at multiple levels, as mixed messaging otherwise undermines progress. Sustained investment in both infrastructure and capacity building is essential, including dedicated staff positions, researcher training and professional development for those implementing reforms.

Critically, alternative outputs such as preprints, preregistrations and open peer review reports are represented inconsistently in today's metadata infrastructure, whilst modular publications are either not indexed or shown with 'placeholder' publication types. This infrastructure gap means that even as practices evolve, they can remain invisible within systems that determine what 'counts' as legitimate scholarship. There is a need for scholarly infrastructures to extend metadata representation for new publication types, as what cannot be found cannot be valued; recent updates within OpenAlex ('Walden' update) appear to make positive progress in this direction.

Opportunities for action

This work has identified opportunities to guide progress towards greater adoption of alternative publishing practices, as follows:

- ▶ **Research funders** should explicitly recognise outputs from alternative practices in assessment criteria, provide dedicated funding streams for platform infrastructure and encourage open sharing practices whilst permitting flexibility in venues.
- ▶ **Research institutions** should revise promotion and tenure criteria to value transparency and reproducibility, support researcher training and invest in enabling infrastructure.
- ▶ **Conventional publishing platforms** should integrate proven alternative practices into existing workflows and adopt metadata schemas to describe emerging publication types.
- ▶ **Alternative publishing platforms** should prioritise sustainability models that reduce reliance on volunteer labour, develop evidence of impact and balance innovation with accessibility.
- ▶ **Infrastructure providers** should extend metadata schemas to represent new publication types, index outputs from alternative platforms and enable linking and citation for non-conventional formats.

The path forward

The transformation is already underway, and the growing adoption of preprinting and open peer review demonstrate that change is possible. The challenge now is ensuring that innovation moves from margins to mainstream not by forcing impossible choices on researchers, but by creating coordinated conditions where rigour, transparency and career advancement align. This requires multiple stakeholders acting simultaneously: systems must enable new practices with minimal friction, disciplinary communities must normalise transparency as core values, and funders and institutions must align evaluation criteria with the behaviours they seek to support.

Figure 3. An illustrative model to continue the transformation.

1. Background and Methodology

This work was commissioned by Knowledge Exchange, a group of national organisations from six European countries working to enable open science by supporting an information infrastructure at an international level. This study seeks to investigate alternative approaches to scholarly publishing and to provide guidance on navigating the current landscape.

Background and objectives

In 2022, Knowledge Exchange initiated a project to explore what alternative publishing platforms do and how they fit within the open scholarly communication ecosystem.

To deliver this work, Knowledge Exchange established a Task and Finish Group and published an initial scoping paper in April 2022 (Sondervan et al., 2022). At that stage, the goal was to develop a taxonomy of platforms that follow different paths compared to conventional publishers, including those pursuing equitable publishing models, different quality control mechanisms, technical features, open-source approaches and iterative publishing workflows.

In September 2023, Knowledge Exchange released the first results from a survey on this subject in a report (Lutz et al., 2023) accompanied by an interactive worksheet (Knowledge Exchange, 2023). The study revealed that most alternative platforms were institution-based and community-driven, with no single discipline appearing more innovative than others. Furthermore, it highlighted that the alternative publishing movement has primarily been an academic response to commercial paywalls and for-profit publishing, focusing on open access rather than radical changes to formats, peer review or research assessment.

This report represents a second phase of investigation, which was launched via a scoping paper published in 2024 (Brandt et al., 2024) with the following goals:

- ▶ to discover how to support innovation in scholarly communication;
- ▶ to gain insights into the maturity and development of alternative publishing platforms; and
- ▶ to develop insights for stakeholders who wish to support or adopt these types of platforms.

Research design

A qualitative approach was adopted due to the exploratory nature of this investigation. Given the limited current understanding of adoption of alternative publishing practices, qualitative methods enabled in-depth exploration of experiences, motivations, barriers and behaviours that quantitative approaches could not capture.

The study consulted three stakeholder groups aligned with the Knowledge Exchange Open Scholarship Framework. The Framework organises activities across three dimensions: the stage of the research life cycle (from discovery through to impact), the arena of interest (political, economic, social, or technological) and the level of organisation (macro/system, meso/community, or micro/individual). This allows mapping of specific open scholarship activities, identifying gaps in current work, and understanding how interventions at different stages and scales affect the research ecosystem. This multi-level approach ensured that the study incorporated perspectives ranging from sector wide policy considerations to the day-to-day publishing decisions of individual researchers.

This project defines **Alternative Publishing Platforms** as innovative channels for scholarly communication that operate outside traditional book and journal publishing frameworks.

In this project, it was decided to focus on platforms that offer a combination of innovative features rather than focusing on one feature only (e.g. only focusing on open peer review; only offering preprint posting).

Figure 1. The Knowledge Exchange Open Scholarship Framework (Neylon, 2017)

A total of 29 participants from Knowledge Exchange countries (Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, the Netherlands and the UK) were interviewed or took part in focus groups, with at least one researcher and one funder from each country. Additional stakeholders from across Europe and North America were included to capture perspectives from platforms with global reach and funding organisations with strategies that actively promote alternative publishing. Interviews targeted representatives of research funding organisations and researchers, whereas focus group engaged representatives of alternative publishing platforms.

Recruitment used convenience sampling and personal networks, targeting stakeholders who were both available and willing to participate. Researchers with experience of alternative publishing platforms proved particularly challenging to engage, either due to high workloads or concerns about insufficient expertise given the relatively early stage of development of this landscape.

A focused literature review conducted using Google

Scholar complemented stakeholder engagement, with an exploratory search spanning 2020-25 to ensure currency. Keyword searches targeted alternative publishing and specific platform names, while citation searches built on core references identified during the scoping phase (Brandt et al., 2024). Results were manually assessed for relevance and inclusion.

All interviews and focus groups were transcribed and thematically coded. Claude.ai (Model: Claude Sonnet 4.5 Extended thinking) assisted in analysing anonymised transcripts to identify patterns and themes, with all AI-generated outputs subject to expert human validation and refinement.

Finally, a bibliometric analysis was undertaken to provide contextual data on publication volumes and growth of alternative publishing platforms, using data sourced from [Dimensions](http://www.dimensions.ai/) (<http://www.dimensions.ai/>), an inter-linked research information system provided by Digital Science and [OpenAlex](https://openalex.org/) (<https://openalex.org/>), a fully-open index of scholarly works.

Analytical framework

Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations theory (Rogers, 2003) provided the analytical framework for exploring factors influencing adoption of alternative publishing. Rogers identifies three critical adopter categories: innovators, early adopters, and the early majority. The theory also proposes five attributes affecting adoption rates: relative advantage (benefits over previous options), compatibility (alignment with existing practices), complexity (ease of understanding and use), trialability (ease of experimentation) and observability (visibility of benefits). This framework enabled systematic analysis of where different alternative publishing practices sit on the adoption curve and which face significant barriers to mainstream uptake.

Limitations

The following limitations should be considered when reading this report:

- ▶ The convenience sampling technique and recruitment through personal networks is likely to have led to the identification and engagement of a non-representative group of stakeholders.
- ▶ As stakeholder engagement focused on specific countries, it may not be appropriate to generalise the findings of this study to research cultures and contexts beyond those consulted.
- ▶ Because of the relatively early stage of development of this landscape, it is possible that not all alternative publishing platforms have been identified and included; no platforms or, more broadly, practices have been excluded intentionally or by design.
- ▶ The analysis is underpinned by thematic coding, which relies on subjective interpretation.
- ▶ This work does not explore long-form publications (e.g. books, monographs), due to their significantly different characteristics, use cases and infrastructures. As a result, the findings presented here should not be extended to these types of outputs.

To counterbalance these limitations, the research data and evidence base have been shared openly.

Furthermore, this project relied on engagement from a Knowledge Exchange core group and an additional Task & Finish Group (see Appendix A), whose expertise helped ensure comprehensive mapping and coverage as well as balanced interpretation of findings.

Supporting publications

More details on this project, as well as supporting evidence (e.g. coded text extracts) can be accessed via Octopus, one of the alternative publishing platforms examined in this project (see (Beucke et al., 2025) for more information).

Research ethics

This project has been ethically approved via the University of Sheffield's Ethics Review Procedure, as administered by the Information School (application no. 066645) (Pinfield et al., 2025).

2. Alternative Publishing Practices and Their Rationale

This section explores alternative publishing practices and their anticipated benefits across three areas: research integrity through transparency, speed and efficiency in publishing and shifts in power dynamics, equity and access. It also discusses the difficulties in pushing for practice changes in a complex system, where early adoption necessarily precedes comprehensive evaluation.

The language of innovation

This investigation began with a straightforward premise: to identify and analyse ‘alternative publishing platforms’ – channels for scholarly communication that operate outside conventional publishing frameworks.

Through an open call, a previous Knowledge Exchange report had identified platforms like Octopus, F1000 Research, ResearchEquals, and Peer Community Journal as exemplars of this space, covering all phases in the research process (see Figure 1). These platforms offer researchers something genuinely different: opportunities to publish non-traditional outputs, engage with open peer review and bypass conventional gatekeepers in scholarly publishing.

Through stakeholder interviews, this study discovered that the term ‘alternative publishing platforms’ felt unfamiliar and somewhat confusing to most participants. Interviewees rarely used this terminology spontaneously, only mirroring it after introduction by the interviewer. More significantly, when the term was presented, several interviewees – particularly research funders – actively pushed back against the framing.

"It's like an ecosystem with different approaches and one doesn't have to be alternative to another. You can of course look at the notion of 'alternative' in terms of the process of publication, but also I look at what the governance and business model of the platform is."

Research Funding Organisation

This type of observation was not just discussing semantics: the resistance highlighted that scholarly communication stakeholders think in terms of what they can do – the practices they can adopt to share research more rapidly, openly, and effectively – as opposed to the infrastructure that enables them to achieve that (i.e. platforms).

This realisation led us to reframing the investigation and analysis compared to the starting point: rather than focusing on platforms, the study shifted to identifying the specific alternative publishing practices that researchers are adopting, understanding why these matter and examining the barriers to their wider

adoption. Although this report focuses on practices, it does so recognising that the infrastructures and platforms available to end users ultimately shape these practices, as well as constrain what can be achieved.

Why ‘practices’ rather than ‘platforms’?

This report deliberately focuses on practices—the specific things researchers do to share their work—rather than platforms that enable those activities. This reframing emerged from stakeholder consultations where ‘alternative publishing platforms’ felt unfamiliar and confusing, but individual practices resonated immediately. In practice, separating practice adoption from platform governance enables researchers to improve their practices within existing workflows while system-level transformation addresses structural issues in parallel.

Alternative Publishing Practices

Through analysis of the platforms that had originally been identified and extensive interviews with researchers, funders and platform providers, six distinct alternative publishing practices emerged as the main areas of focus for this work.

These practices represent meaningful departures (yet with varying magnitude) from conventional scholarly communication, each addressing specific limitations in traditional publishing workflows (see Figure 2).

Focusing on practices rather than platforms clarifies what is specifically changing in scholarly communication today. Platforms come and go, merge, pivot their business models and evolve their features. However, the practices – the specific things researchers do to share their work – can persist and spread across multiple platforms and contexts.

Preprint posting is a prime example of this: the practice is no longer confined to dedicated preprint servers. Journals now accept submissions that originated as preprints, funders recognise preprints in grant applications and researchers cite preprints in published papers. The practice has become embedded in research workflows across multiple platforms and stakeholder groups, and no single type of platform ‘owns’ preprinting anymore.

This practices-centric view also reveals that what makes a platform "truly alternative" (using the terminology of the original Knowledge Exchange study) is not any single feature, but the bundling of multiple non-conventional practices into integrated workflows. For example:

- ▶ F1000 Research combines preprinting, open peer review and versioning.
- ▶ Octopus offers modular publishing with open review.
- ▶ Peer Community Journal integrates curation after publication with open reports.

These combinations create qualitatively different publishing experiences that go beyond incremental improvements to traditional models.

The focus on practices also acknowledges that the term 'alternative' is contextually dependent and temporally bound: a practice is only alternative relative to what is conventional in a particular research community at a particular moment. For example, preprinting is now mainstream in physics but remains alternative in many humanities disciplines, and open peer review is conventional for some journals but alternative for others.

As practices gain adoption, they cease to be alternative and become simply how research is shared. The term 'alternative' thus describes the current state of practices, not their intrinsic characteristics. Sections 3 and 4 explore these concepts in more detail, bridging the gap between current state, adoption trends and long-term change in scholarly communication.

However, alternative publishing practices face a fundamental barrier to recognition and adoption. Newer publication types created through alternative publishing practices tend not be explicitly reflected in existing metadata schema such as Crossref or DataCite. This infrastructure recognition operates at other levels, too, including indexes like OpenAlex, Web of Science, Scopus or Dimensions, Current Research Information Systems and grant application or impact tracking portals.

This infrastructure gap means that even as practices evolve and gain traction, they may remain invisible

within the systems that determine what 'counts' as legitimate scholarship.

Why these practices matter

The core premise of alternative publishing practices is that they can help address a broad range of challenges in scholarly communication.

Yet our literature review revealed a significant gap, as there is extensive discussion of anticipated benefits but limited documentation of real-world implementation or impact. While the theoretical case for these practices is well-articulated, empirical evidence about whether they deliver on their promises is partial. Understanding this gap between aspiration and evidence was central to this project.

Despite this evidence gap, the benefits these practices seek to provide align precisely with the system failures that major international reform initiatives are trying to address—notably funding and research assessment frameworks that can incentivise perverse behaviours and lead to a perception that publication itself the main aim (HM Government, 2025).

Today, 782 organisations have signed Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment commitments (CoARA, 2025). More than 25,000 individuals and organisations have endorsed the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA, 2025). Furthermore, the growing popularity of the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information (Barcelona Declaration, 2025) is an important signal that scholarly communication is not working for all.

The literature review carried out in this project identified three major categories of anticipated benefits that emerged consistently across the literature on alternative publishing: improved research integrity through transparency and openness, increased speed and efficiency in publishing and shifts in power dynamics, equity and access. The sections below examine each of these themes in turn, exploring both their theoretical basis and what is currently known about their realisation in practice.

Research integrity through transparency

Conventional publishing involves editorial and format constraints that can limit visibility into the research process. For example, methods sections must fit journal word limits, negative results often go unpublished and peer review typically occurs confidentially. The published account therefore represents a polished final product rather than documenting the iterative, uncertain process through which research develops.

"The data is the finding. The concept that you can't actually see the outcome of the research, you've just got to take the summary and the narrative and base it out of that just seems mad. That's why we were like: you need to have the methods, you need to have the data, you need to have the code."

Alternative Publishing Platform

These structural features have direct implications for reproducibility. When other researchers struggle to reproduce findings, they often cannot determine whether difficulties stem from the original study, their replication attempt or subtle methodological details that were compressed or omitted to meet publication requirements. The reproducibility crisis (Baker, 2016) has highlighted tensions between conventional publication formats and the level of detail needed to fully assess and replicate research.

Alternative publishing practices aim to tackle this problem directly in various ways:

- ▶ Preprint posting, open peer review and curation after publication make peer feedback visible, so that readers see comments, author responses and how research evolves (including through versioning).
- ▶ Modular publishing separates hypotheses, methods, results and interpretations into independent components, making it harder to present post-hoc storytelling as confirmatory research. A similar effect is achieved through preregistration.

The emphasis on publishing in prestigious journals can encourage researchers to prioritise narrative coherence over full transparency about methodological complexities. Proponents of alternative publishing

practices as well as broader movements like CoARA argue that there is a need to shift these incentives by changing what counts as a legitimate publication and by providing venues where the iterative nature of research is expected rather than edited out.

Speed and efficiency

Peer review is widely recognised as a slow and time-consuming process, but its deliberate pace reflects the rigour and care that underpin trustworthy scholarship. Authors nonetheless often wait months, sometimes years, for feedback and publication decisions.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the implications of a slow pace of sharing became very apparent, as crucial findings risked reaching public health authorities with too long a delay (Fraser et al., 2021). Even in more everyday circumstances, delays in sharing can stall anyone relying on access to research findings; indeed, work can easily become outdated if research is disseminated more slowly than modern knowledge production demands.

"We have some problems because the process from submitting a manuscript to being published takes too long a time."

Researcher

Alternative publishing practices seek to break these bottlenecks:

- ▶ Preprints bypass peer review entirely for initial dissemination, allowing immediate sharing while review proceeds.
- ▶ Models like publish-review-curate decouple peer review from publication logistics, potentially speeding the review process itself.
- ▶ Post-publication review eliminates delays altogether, making review continuous rather than a pre-publication gate.

Yet, speed creates tension with quality. Though peer review is understood to be imperfect, it is also often seen as the best approach available today to catch errors and improve manuscripts before publication.

As a result, the question is not whether alternative platforms can accelerate publishing but whether they can do so while maintaining or improving the quality control that peer review, despite its flaws, provides.

Power, equity and access

Some founders of alternative publishing platforms explicitly aimed to shift power dynamics in scholarly publishing, addressing concerns that extend beyond individual researcher convenience to fundamental questions about who controls knowledge production and who can access it.

Today's publishing ecosystem reflects a complex interplay between commercial publishers, academic institutions and the broader research community. Large publishers increasingly control not just dissemination but also the discovery, evaluation and curation of scholarly outputs, often monetising work that is publicly funded.

Beyond the published outputs themselves, large organisations control increasingly significant portions of the scholarly communication infrastructure, including citation indexes, research metrics, discovery platforms, data repositories and metadata. Alternative publishing platforms that offer open infrastructure and transparent metadata represent attempts to reclaim this layer of control as a public good.

This concentration of control creates several interconnected challenges:

- ▶ Research institutions bear substantial subscription and open access fees, often covered through a mix of public funds and research grants, while ceding management of their intellectual outputs.
- ▶ Prestige hierarchies become entrenched, concentrating visibility and recognition within well-funded institutions, established disciplines and high-impact journals, which can marginalise emerging voices and interdisciplinary work as well as promoting a transactional culture.
- ▶ Restrictive access models constrain public engagement with research, limiting societal impact and raising ethical questions about privatising knowledge generated through public investment.

Understanding these structural issues is essential for assessing the potential of alternative publishing practices. For example, a commercial publisher could adopt all six practices examined in this report and deliver meaningful improvements in transparency, speed and methodological rigour. However, such adoption would not address concentration of market power, governance of scholarly infrastructure or fundamental questions about who benefits from scholarly communication.

“There's an issue around sustainability for a lot of these platforms, especially the ones that are open source or community led... [...] It becomes harder to maintain them and a lot of those are maintained by communities, often based on volunteer labour.”
Researcher

These system-level concerns may seem abstract compared to immediate practical questions about where to publish or how to advance one's career. Yet, structural issues have direct implications on long-term sustainability, institutional autonomy and incentives.

Making progress with limited direct evidence

The arguments discussed in the previous sections rest largely on theoretical analysis and platform design rather than empirical evidence, as research in this area continues to develop alongside growing investment in metaresearch and the relatively slow pace of culture and practice change. It should be noted that this lack of empirical evidence is not meant as criticism. Indeed, this is not unusual for innovation in complex systems, where early adoption necessarily precedes comprehensive evaluation.

At the same time, the alignment between the benefits offered by alternative publishing practices (or platforms) and reform priorities is an important signal and highlights that developing an evidence base in this domain is a desirable endeavour. If alternative publishing practices (or platforms) are seen as viable mechanisms for achieving reform goals, understanding what enables their success and how to scale it is especially important. Equally, identifying where platforms face challenges or fail to achieve anticipated benefits can inform both platform development and broader reform strategies.

Furthermore, the bibliometric analysis carried out as part of this project yielded an important result: alternative outputs such as preprints, preregistrations and open peer review reports are represented inconsistently in today's metadata infrastructure. For example, new versions or research objects often show as completely separate publications, and peer reviews are represented and versioned differently across platforms. Modular publications face even greater challenges: they are either not indexed or shown with 'placeholder' publication types that do not entirely reflect the nature of the relevant research object. The OpenAlex 'Walden' update appears to be making positive steps in this direction; although this took place beyond the analysis phase of the present study, [Jisc highlighted \(https://emails.jisc.ac.uk/q/17J8ywlqE7FnSleN636CLk/wv\)](https://emails.jisc.ac.uk/q/17J8ywlqE7FnSleN636CLk/wv) that publications via the Octopus platform are now findable within OpenAlex.

The following section addresses these questions by investigating what happens when researchers and institutions engage with alternative publishing practices, documenting their experiences and what they mean for the future of scholarly communication.

Figure 2. Alternative publishing practices examined in this project (readers should note that preregistration, preprints posting and the open sharing of peer review reports may be considered as forms of modular publication).

Open peer review

Makes the review process transparent by publishing peer review reports alongside research outputs. Open peer review reports may be shared anonymously or signed, with no established custom in today's landscape. This stands in contrast to traditional double-anonymous peer review and addresses long-standing concerns about bias, quality and accountability. Some journals began experimenting with open peer review in the late 1990s, and the practice is being increasingly adopted by mainstream venues today.

Review and curation after publication

Break research dissemination into sequential stages. Researchers first publish their work (typically as a preprint), experts or communities then review it openly and, finally, editors curate reviewed research into collections. Unlike traditional journals where editorial selection happens before publication, this approach inverts the process. Anyone can become an editor and apply their own criteria for quality and importance. This practice emerged from overlay journals built on arXiv in the late 1990s and has recently gained more traction with the adoption of the Publish, Review, Curate model by eLife.

Modular publication

Breaks research into standalone, publishable units – individual hypotheses, methods, datasets or findings – rather than requiring complete, article-length papers. Dedicated platforms link these publications into chains that span the entire research lifecycle, from initial ideas through final interpretation. Each unit can be published, reviewed and cited independently. This practice challenges the traditional research article format and enables sharing of work that might not fit into conventional publications: negative results, methodological innovations or preliminary findings. Platforms like Octopus and ResearchEquals emerged in the early 2020s to support this approach, though the concept of publishing smaller research units dates to earlier platforms like microPublication Biology (2016-) and PLOS Currents (2009-2018).

3. Adoption of Alternative Publishing Practices

This section analyses adoption patterns across the alternative publishing practices considered and categorises these into three scenarios based on adoption likelihood: ‘within reach’ (preprint posting, open peer review), ‘evolution’ (preregistration, curation after publication, versioning), and ‘revolution’ (modular publications). The analysis focuses primarily on the researcher’s perspective, to identify potential ways forward and key pathways for future action.

While alternative publishing platforms bundle together multiple innovations – from preprint posting to open peer review to modular publication – these individual practices vary significantly in how easily they can be adopted by authors and researchers. Understanding this variation is critical to explaining why uptake remains uneven across the research community.

Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations theory (Rogers, 2003) provides a useful framework for understanding why some alternative publishing practices spread more rapidly than others: when the innovations offered by alternative publishing platforms are mapped against relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability and observability, stark differences emerge.

This section outlines three scenarios that would enable greater adoption of the alternative practices under investigation, based on the evidence collected through desk research and the stakeholder consultation (see Table 1). A more detailed mapping of practices to Diffusion of Innovations theory is shown in Table 2.

It should be noted that the mapping in Tables 1 and 2 is intended as a snapshot: for example, preprint posting would have been categorised as a 'Revolution' not long ago, and some may still consider open peer review to fall beyond the 'Within reach'. Additionally, while the scenarios in Table 1 helpfully characterise the dynamics behind increasing the adoption of new publishing practices, they require an important caveat: the critical barrier often lies not in the complexity of the practices themselves (which affects the micro level, per Figure 1), but in the incentive structures and cultural norms that surround their adoption, including within and across disciplines (which are at the meso and macro levels in the system).

The gap, which is further explored in Section 4, reflects the reality that the publishing choices of researchers are heavily constrained by institutional evaluation criteria, disciplinary norms and career progression requirements (European Commission, 2019). As discussed in the remainder of this section, even highly compatible innovations face adoption challenges when they carry perceived career risk, for example for early career researchers who feel they cannot afford to publish in unrecognised venues.

Table 1: Adoption scenarios for alternative publishing practices.

Category	Key features	Greater adoption of...
Within reach	High compatibility with current publishing practices and minimal (if any) risks to adopters	Preprinting; Open peer review
Evolution	Some compatibility with current publishing practices but potential risks to adopters	Preregistration; Review and curation after publication; Versioning
Revolution	Low compatibility with current publishing practices but risks to adopters	Modular publications

▶ Within reach

Preprint posting

Some innovations fit relatively seamlessly into existing research workflows, and preprint posting exemplifies this well in some disciplines (as noted in Section 2). A representative of a research funding organisation explained how preprints have become normalised within their specific community:

"[Preprinting] became basically, for want of a better word, cool among researchers. And when that happens, change happens even in the absence of policies."

Research Funding Organisation

Importantly, preprint adoption currently varies (Rzayeva et al., 2025). The physical and mathematical sciences show the highest rates of preprint adoption, particularly amongst researchers in the Americas and Europe. In recent years, uptake has also grown significantly in the

information and computing sciences and the life and medical sciences, driven primarily by researchers in North America and Western and Northern Europe. By contrast, preprints remain relatively uncommon in the humanities and the social and behavioural sciences. Asia demonstrates consistently low adoption across most disciplines, though Eastern Asia has shown modest recent growth. These patterns reveal that preprint adoption is shaped by the interaction between disciplinary culture and regional research practices.

The compatibility of preprints extends beyond cultural acceptance. They work alongside traditional publishing rather than replacing it (Chtena et al., 2025). Researchers can post preprints while simultaneously pursuing conventional journal publication, reducing perceived risks.

The relative advantage of preprints is also immediately visible: faster dissemination, earlier feedback and establishing priority for ideas (Chiarelli et al., 2019).

"Speed was an important factor in terms of your initial willing to try something different... I guess most people would always be frustrated about how long it takes for a review process."

Researcher

These benefits accrue to individual researchers without requiring wholesale changes to how they evaluate or structure their work. Preprints are also trialable, as researchers can experiment with posting one or two preprints before committing to the practice more broadly as their default behaviour.

At the same time, it must be acknowledged that broad acceptance of preprints across disciplines is a relatively recent phenomenon. Initially, many communities—particularly in the life and biomedical sciences—and publishers opposed this practice, in some cases arguing that it would constitute 'prior publication' and would therefore render work unsuitable for journal submission.

Open peer review

Open peer review exemplifies innovations where systemic benefits outweigh individual costs, with

adoption remaining limited because those costs fall on individuals while benefits accrue collectively. As most of today's reward and recognition structures do not explicitly recognise service contributions such as open peer review, individual motivation to engage with the practice remains a key barrier.

Beyond transparency, open peer review reports can improve review quality, help readers understand the strengths and weaknesses of the work as perceived by peer reviewers, provide training for early career researchers and enable research on the peer review process itself (Henriquez, 2023). While open peer review is compatible with existing editorial workflows (Ross-Hellauer & Horbach, 2024), technological infrastructure remains underdeveloped and implementation across mainstream publishing platforms has so far been limited.

The main concerns that are shared by stakeholders are around signed peer review reports, i.e. cases where the commentary is not only made available to the public but also the identity of the peer reviewer is open (Ross-Hellauer, 2017). Indeed, a representative of a research funding organisation identified the naming component as a critical barrier:

"I think having these reports openly available is gaining acceptance. Very slowly, but having names on it is... maybe the most difficult part. The reviewers themselves may find it difficult to be critical about work of their colleagues and them being named."

Research Funding Organisation

Career stage and institutional hierarchies can amplify these concerns. A researcher noted:

"I wasn't really that comfortable in signing reviews while still being a PhD student and not being sure if I was actually allowed to review."

Researcher

Despite these barriers, some researchers report positive experiences when open review is combined with other innovations, suggesting that the practice may be easier to adopt when packaged with other changes.

▶ Evolution

Preregistration

Preregistration exemplifies innovations that offer clear methodological benefits but require significant upfront investment, as researchers must specify their hypotheses, methods and analysis plans before starting their work. This practice is primarily applicable to deductive research that seeks to test hypotheses and less suited to qualitative or inductive studies that require methodological flexibility.

The registered report format, which combines preregistration with staged peer review, intensifies both benefits and costs (Sarafoglou et al., 2022). One researcher explained the appeal:

"Especially for empirical quantitative articles, [preregistration] is probably the best format out there right now. Reviewers feel that they actually have something to say, something to contribute to the research. It feels more like they're like colleagues that improve the design rather than reviewers who try to completely dismiss your idea."

Researcher

However, the upfront time investment at the beginning of a project is substantial. As one early career researcher noted:

"Writing a registered report takes a long time because you already have to have figured out methods and analyses first without looking at the data. And basically have written half of the paper before you do the stage one review and then you are waiting for the review."

Researcher

Because of this, preregistration is more common in medical research (where it is mandatory in several countries) and social and behavioural sciences. These are areas with significant implications for human health, where transparency and rigour are especially critical to ensure reliable and trustworthy findings (Cashin et al., 2023). These extended timelines fall particularly heavily

on those with precarious positions. The same researcher continued:

"I don't think people always have time for it within the time frame of a PhD or like a postdoc. So I do think that is a bit less accessible time wise to do these things for early career researchers."

Researcher

The complexity extends beyond individual researchers. A representative of an alternative publishing platform emphasised that not all journals are equally capable of supporting the pre-registration process and its implications.

Review and curation after publication

Review and curation after publication, which are often discussed in the format of the publish-review-curate model, represent a middle ground in compatibility with current publishing practices. This approach, where researchers publish preprints, which are then openly peer-reviewed and curated into collections, requires more behavioural change than preprint posting alone but less than the complete restructuring of research outputs required by modular publication.

The key challenge with this model is coordination. While researchers can independently post preprints, the review and curation stages depend on community infrastructure and voluntary effort. The model offers clear advantages – transparent peer review, faster publication, flexibility (eLife, 2024) – but also introduces complexity around timing, reviewer recruitment, and subsequent journal publication. Some proponents of the peer-review-curate model argue that journal publication would not be necessary in light of the curation element of the approach. However, current career incentives remain centred around established approaches to publication, which hinders a full transformation.

Versioning

Versioning – the ability to update and improve research outputs over time – is a compatible innovation (as demonstrated by preprints themselves) but carries surprisingly complex adoption dynamics. The concept

of versioning aligns naturally with how researchers think about their work as evolving, yet traditional publishing systems resist the creation of multiple versions, first and foremost through the concept of a version of record (Hincliffe, 2022).

One researcher articulated the frustration:

"I really hate mistakes in papers and then people not correcting them... Like if you have a very successful book you would also have a second edition and take care of mistakes you know make it better... For books this is a normal thing."

Researcher

Furthermore, a representative of an alternative publishing platform described the potential advantages:

"Instead of basing clinical guidelines on a systematic review, which invariably is several years out of date by the time it's published. if you make it living, it means every time a new clinical trial comes in, you can just update the article."

Alternative Publishing Platform

Yet, today's research culture and publishing practices sometimes frame corrections in a way that may give rise to (perceptions of) reputational damage. A researcher discovered this directly when attempting to fix errors:

"I found out that the correction is not really putting a better pdf on the Internet. It's having the old pdf and then another pdf with some text about the correction."

Researcher

The complexity increases when versioning intersects with peer review and citation. For example, decisions taken in the context of peer review may not transfer to subsequent versions depending on the changes made. For some researchers, particularly in fast-moving fields, versioning has become normalised practice, especially in combination with preprint posting (Moshontz et al., 2021). However, adoption across the research landscape

remains uneven, not least because versioning is not directly compatible with evaluation systems that demand fixed, unchanging records of achievement.

▶ Revolution

Modular publication

At the far end of the adoption spectrum lie innovations that require fundamental reconceptualisation of scholarly publishing. These innovations are categorically different from the status quo, not simply harder: modular publication platforms – which ask researchers to break traditional research articles into discrete components like hypotheses, methods, results and analyses (Dhar, 2023) – represent the most disruptive innovations in the current landscape.

The relative advantage of modular publication is less immediately obvious to individual researchers. While the approach promises better recognition for diverse contributions, more granular credit attribution and faster sharing of incremental findings (Hsing et al., 2023), these benefits accrue primarily at the system level through enabling more rapid knowledge sharing and wider participation in scholarly discourse.

Individual researchers also face significant upfront costs: learning new workflows, restructuring how they conceptualise research, and, most critically, uncertainty about whether these contributions will be recognised in career evaluation.

The complexity barrier is substantial, and similarity to or alignment with mainstream publishing practices is a significant driver of adoption:

"Platforms like F1000 have got over that tipping point, but in a sense that's easier. They're not that far away from a traditional publishing platform. They're certainly a lot closer to a traditional scholarly journal than something like Octopus."

Research Funding Organisation

A representative of an alternative publishing platform articulated the adoption challenge sharply:

"When it comes to actually writing up work and publishing it, motivation drops off because the institutional benefits and the incentives [researchers] have in their career don't point to [modular publishing] as definitely being something that would be beneficial. So they'd be taking a risk."

Alternative Publishing Platform

It is therefore researchers who are most motivated to experiment with new approaches to scholarly communication and open research that tend to engage with significantly disruptive publishing models:

"My motivation is just personal interest and personal motivation... I'm really interested and convinced by the philosophy of open science. I really think that it needs to be the future of research – even if now it's not the most popular way to publish."

Researcher

Other researchers echoed this philosophical commitment, emphasising how openness served both personal and systemic goals. Freedom was also mentioned as an important aspect, both through seniority (e.g. senior academics no longer needing to conform with established practices) and external requirements (e.g. no specified acceptable publication venues in institutional or grant conditions):

"My current funder doesn't have any demands on where to publish so they allow me to go for those channels. I live in a bubble and that's not good because it's not representative."

Researcher

Because of their disruptive characteristics, these practices may never achieve mainstream adoption in their current form: their main function today is to explore possibilities and inform system evolution.

The influence of support from funders and research performing organisations

The adoption patterns described above are significantly influenced by the extent to which funders and institutions actively endorse and support alternative publishing practices. When influential organisations

signal legitimacy through policies, funding or explicit encouragement, they can accelerate movement along the adoption curve. The most direct impact can be realised in the case of practices in the 'within reach' category, although support is also valuable for practices in the 'evolution' category that offer clear benefits but carry perceived risks.

Funder endorsement operates as a powerful legitimising mechanism. When major research funders explicitly permit or encourage alternative outputs, they reduce career risk for individual researchers and can affect disciplinary norms about what constitutes acceptable publication venues. This endorsement can take various forms, from permissive policies that allow researchers to cite preprints in grant applications to mandates requiring specific practices like preregistration or data sharing.

Examples include direct funding instruments dedicated to scholarly communication innovation (such as the French Open Science Fund, the funding of Octopus by Research England and the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)-funded National Service Centre for Diamond Open Access); community-driven funding models; and interventionist approaches by major funders (for instance, the promotion of preprint posting by the Gates Foundation (Gates Foundation, 2024) and the Howard Hughes Medical Institute (Office of the President, 2025)).

However, the evidence also shows that endorsement alone is insufficient. Several participants noted how funders may permit or even encourage alternative publishing practices, but institutional evaluation criteria remain largely tied to conventional metrics. This misalignment creates mixed signals that ultimately undermine progress, as researchers must still navigate promotion and tenure systems that may not recognise outputs from alternative practices.

The effectiveness of funder and institutional support thus depends on coordination across levels: macro-level policies must align with meso-level disciplinary cultures and micro-level individual incentives. Without this coordination, even well-intentioned endorsement may fail to shift adoption patterns meaningfully.

The implications of unequal rates of adoption

Each alternative publishing practice carries different combinations of relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability and observability. Understanding these differences is essential because it reveals that the problem is not primarily about platform design or researcher awareness. Rather, adoption barriers are deeply embedded in how scholarly communication systems operate.

Compatible innovations like preprints can spread through grassroots adoption and gradual normalisation, though even these face discipline-specific barriers. Innovations requiring moderate change – preregistration, review and curation after publication, versioning – can succeed within supportive communities but struggle to scale without coordinated infrastructure and incentive changes. Disruptive innovations require wholesale transformation of evaluation systems, career structures and disciplinary norms.

Overall, the current landscape reflects not researcher conservatism but a combination of factors: for some, rational responses to the characteristics of innovations in the context of institutional realities; for many others, adherence to established publishing norms.

Where researchers have encountered and considered alternative practices, they tend to adopt those offering clear individual benefits within existing systems and resist those demanding personal risk without corresponding career rewards. For example, researchers may:

- ▶ Embrace versioning in principle but encounter systems that penalise corrections;
- ▶ Appreciate the methodological rigour of preregistration whilst being unable to spare the time costs given precarious employment; or
- ▶ Recognise the value of open peer review but rationally protect themselves from reputational risks.

However, for the majority whose publishing behaviour remains shaped primarily by scientific socialisation, disciplinary conventions and institutional norms, the question of alternatives may never arise. Publishing in conventional venues is simply what they have learned and always known, rather than a choice consciously weighed against other options.

This pattern also points towards the fact that many of the innovations that promise the greatest systemic

benefits are precisely those that are least adoptable under current incentive structures. On the other hand, the innovations most compatible with existing systems mainly offer incremental improvements that are less likely to appear on the radar of authors acting in line with established customs.

The core implication is that transformative potential is available but is facing virtually insurmountable adoption barriers without coordinated intervention at institutional, funder and disciplinary levels.

“The university gets funding based on the number of peer reviewed publications in journals. So it's the politics also. If we can publish in those journals, then we should stick to that... Without any publications in those journals, no funding.”

Researcher

Table 2: Mapping publishing practices to the five innovation attributes that influence adoption rates by authors.

► **Table 2a: Within reach**

Publishing practice	Relative advantage	Compatibility	Complexity	Trialability	Observability
Preprinting	Provides faster dissemination and early feedback	Already being implemented across mainstream systems and can work as a supplement to traditional publishing	Relatively straightforward	Easy to try with minimal risks	The benefits of adopting preprinting are highly visible; fast dissemination is advantageous, though early feedback is not common
Open peer review	Provides largely potential and systemic advantages related to transparency	Already being implemented across mainstream systems	Relatively straightforward, though there are different models for the author to understand and navigate	Fairly easy to try across mainstream conventional platforms where it is offered; also trialable as part of curation after publication, e.g. via preprint servers	The benefits of adopting open peer review are not easily visible at the individual level

▶ Table 2b: Evolution

Publishing practice	Relative advantage	Compatibility	Complexity	Trialability	Observability
Preregistration	Provides dissemination and early feedback at a potentially transformative point	Already works as supplement to traditional publishing in a range of disciplines	Additional task with significant complexity and demands on a researcher's time, though expected in some disciplines	Easy to try though time consuming and likely unfamiliar for fields where it is not expected	The benefits of adopting preregistration are highly visible in fields where this is expected (e.g. medical sciences) but less visible in other cases
Review and curation after publication	Provides freedom to publish rapidly and openly in scholar-led venues	Typically incompatible with mainstream conventional platforms; requires new platforms (e.g. overlay journals)	New and potentially unfamiliar tasks with significant complexity and demands on the time of authors and curators	Difficult to try, as it depends on preprinting and open peer review, as well as dedicated platforms	The benefits of adopting review and curation after publication are not easily visible at the individual level
Versioning	Provides largely potential and systemic advantages related with the correction of errors or changes over time	Already being implemented by preprint servers; potentially compatible with mainstream conventional platforms	Relatively straightforward on preprint servers; not simple on mainstream conventional platforms	Easy to try as part of preprint servers, but less visible if presented as an option embedded in conventional publishing workflows	The benefits of adopting versioning are not easily visible at the individual level, unless they are direct corrections of published work

▶ Table 2c: Revolution

Publishing practice	Relative advantage	Compatibility	Complexity	Trialability	Observability
Modular publications	Provides faster dissemination and early feedback on smaller elements of a research endeavour	Typically incompatible with mainstream conventional platforms; requires new platforms	New and potentially unfamiliar tasks with significant complexity and demands on the time of authors and readers	Cannot meaningfully try without fully committing to the modular approach; high switching costs	The benefits of adopting modular publications are not easily visible at the individual level

4. The Path Forward

This section explores a transformation strategy whereby alternative practices are embedded within mainstream infrastructure once proven viable and beneficial through alternative platforms or other forms of experimentation and innovation.

Success depends on three key enablers: coordinated action across stakeholders, reform of research assessment systems, and sustained investment in infrastructure and capacity.

Practices over platforms

The evidence reveals an imbalance in the adoption of alternative publishing practices. Researchers, research funding organisations and platform providers all recognise the value of these: transparency through open review, rigour through preregistration, accessibility through preprinting, granularity through modular publication. Yet, adoption remains limited and concentrated among early adopters; it often occurs despite rather than because of career incentives.

This situation stems from the misalignment between innovative practices and reward and recognition in research:

- ▶ Established publishing venues offer career recognition but limited innovation.
- ▶ Alternative platforms offer innovation but uncertain career recognition.

Researchers caught between these options have to make rational choices: they adopt compatible practices like preprinting that supplement traditional publishing, while avoiding disruptive practices like modular publication that require higher risks and wholesale commitment to unfamiliar venues.

Furthermore, the imbalance in adoption affects researchers differently depending on disciplinary context and career stage:

- ▶ Representatives of alternative publishing platform and researchers both noted how publishing norms vary across disciplines, with some fields more accepting of preprints, open review or registered reports than others.
- ▶ Career stage introduces additional complexity. Early career researchers face particular pressure to demonstrate success in traditional publishing for hiring and tenure decisions. On the other hand, more established researchers often have greater freedom to experiment. However, even senior researchers acknowledge operating ‘in a bubble’ when engaging with alternative publishing, recognising that their choices remain unrepresentative of mainstream behaviour.

Continuing the transformation

Significant shifts to established practices will require strategic interventions that remove the perceived trade-off between methodological rigour, transparency and career advancement. The status quo, which sees alternative platforms as competitors to conventional publishing, creates an impossible choice for most researchers.

Transformation is more usefully understood as a cyclical process in which new practices are developed, tested, and progressively embedded within mainstream scholarly communication (see Figure 3). This illustrative model operates through consecutive phases, each led by different actors within the research ecosystem, and depends on the interplay between experimental spaces that generate innovation and mainstream infrastructures that can deliver scale.

Within this cycle, the first phase is **experimentation and demonstration**, most often led by research communities, funders and institutions. Alternative publishing practices require dedicated spaces for innovation before they can be meaningfully assessed or embedded in mainstream infrastructure. These experimental settings (whether alternative platforms, pilot programmes or community-led initiatives) provide controlled environments where practices can be tested and demonstrated by actors seeking to challenge conventional approaches, without forcing others to navigate the full career risks of early adoption.

This experimentation serves multiple functions for the broader publishing ecosystem: it enables quick exploration of new technologies and ways of working that are not tied to existing infrastructures and financial drivers; it allows practices to mature through iteration and feedback, generating evidence about what works and what does not work; and it creates proofs of concept that shift expectations within disciplinary communities, effectively moving the Overton window (Mackinac Center, 2019) for what counts as legitimate scholarly communication.

Importantly, these efforts are frequently pursued in response to the developing needs and goals of research communities, funders and institutions. Indeed, representatives of alternative publishing platforms

described how some researchers engage with experimental practices to help shift power dynamics in scholarly communication: reappropriating control from commercial publishers, reducing system costs or returning power to scientific communities. The practice of experimentation represents research and development for scholarly communication itself.

Once practices have been tested and their value demonstrated, **mainstream adoption** can follow, led by infrastructure and service providers, funders and publishing organisations. This phase focuses on bringing innovative practices that are receiving growing attention to infrastructures and platforms that already serve researchers at scale. Infrastructures and service providers, as well as publishing organisations, can respond to demonstrated demand and competitive pressure and adopt practices that have been proven effective.

Embedding alternative publishing practices within existing channels might include, for example: depositing preprints automatically upon journal submission where this has not been done by the author; providing transparent peer review processes in existing journals, with optional open or signed reviews; providing greater integration of preprint servers and data repositories with other scholarly publishing infrastructures; and enabling modular submission options for complex research outputs. It should be noted that implementing such changes and integrations typically requires significant technical expertise and resources, advantages that large publishing organisations often possess but which may require capacity building in the case of smaller and publicly funded organisations.

Importantly, this embedding process is not unidirectional. Alternative platforms themselves may moderate their more radical features to gain mainstream acceptance and wider adoption. For instance, a platform initially built around mandatory open peer review might make it optional, or one designed for modular publication might add traditional article formats. While this adaptation can broaden reach and reduce barriers to adoption, it also raises questions about whether the transformative potential of certain practices is diluted in the process of achieving scale. It is, therefore, important to distinguish between productive evolution that maintains core benefits while

improving accessibility, and dilution that sacrifices the very innovations that made these practices valuable.

Representatives of alternative publishing platforms acknowledged that the proliferation of different approaches and nuanced variations, while valuable for experimentation, creates confusion for researchers navigating scholarly communication. Whether through mainstream venues adopting proven practices or alternative platforms moderating their approaches, reducing this confusion enables researchers to adopt methodological improvements without learning entirely new systems or sacrificing their choice of venue.

As mainstream infrastructures adopt proven practices and these become available through familiar channels and established venues, **researcher-side risk is reduced**. However, infrastructure availability alone is insufficient to reduce risk: hiring, promotion and funding decisions must evolve in the same direction to enable material progress. Meaningful risk reduction therefore requires alignment between infrastructure development and reform of the evaluative frameworks that shape researcher behaviour. When both dimensions are addressed, **normalisation and scale** can follow: previously radical ideas become standard practice, and the cycle can begin again as new approaches emerge to address remaining challenges or respond to evolving needs.

It is important to recognise that not all practices will complete this cycle. For practices in the 'revolution' category (see Table 1), experimental spaces may not be a temporary incubator but a permanent home. The core value of these practices lies in exploring fundamentally different alternatives that may serve communities whose needs current systems cannot meet. In line with this, limited or slow adoption should not be seen as a problem or commercial failure. Some practices may never scale beyond experimental settings, yet still provide valuable insights that inform mainstream evolution; others may take years to demonstrate their value before broader uptake becomes feasible. Critics may argue that supporting parallel experiments risks fragmenting effort and diverting scarce funding from proven infrastructures or other research areas. However, diversity of experimentation is essential to discover which models genuinely serve different communities and to ensure that progress is not constrained by existing market logics or inertia.

It should be noted that the division of responsibilities within the cycle (see Figure 3) creates a structural risk that warrants explicit recognition, as commercial service providers are often best placed to scale innovations when funders, institutions or communities lack the capacity to do so. As a result, the transition from experimentation to adoption is frequently mediated by commercial incentives rather than collective priorities, which, in turn, can result in selective uptake. Practices that are commercially advantageous or inexpensive to integrate are more readily absorbed into mainstream infrastructure, while those requiring significant investment or posing disruptive implications for existing business models are sidelined. Moreover, innovations originally developed in open or community-led settings may be commercialised in ways that limit competition or re-centralise control, reinforcing the very power imbalances that experimental approaches sought to challenge. Thus, while the cyclical model offers a practical route for mainstreaming beneficial practices, its transformative potential will not be realised unless funders, institutions and research communities play a more active role in sustaining and scaling innovations beyond the experimental phase.

Key enablers

Overall, without sustained public investment towards research and development for scholarly communication infrastructure, the experimentation essential for system transformation cannot occur at meaningful scale. The success of this cyclical approach to innovation in scholarly communication depends on addressing three prerequisites that emerged consistently across stakeholder perspectives and have been introduced in the discussion above: coordinated action, reform of research assessment and sustained investment in infrastructure and people.

Collective action and coordination

Large-scale transformation cannot occur through isolated initiatives. The evidence reveals that funders, institutions, disciplinary communities and platform providers are currently caught in a waiting game, each looking to others to move first. Breaking this impasse requires deliberate coordination (or, indeed, a bold first mover).

As a research funder emphasised, all three aspects of the system – infrastructure, disciplines, and institutional policies – must be addressed in parallel, "not one before the other." This observation directly reflects the structure of the Open Scholarship Framework: meaningful transformation requires simultaneous intervention at macro level (policies and evaluation systems), meso level (disciplinary cultures and community infrastructure) and micro level (individual researcher practices and skills). Sequential approaches that attempt to change one level before addressing others inevitably stall, as each level constrains and enables the others.

As a result, without coordination, mixed messaging will necessarily undermine progress: for example, funders may encourage preprinting while institutions reward traditional metrics; platforms may demonstrate new possibilities while evaluation committees disregard them.

Existing international bodies across research and scholarly communication are well-placed to take action in this space, including for example Science Europe and cOAlition S (representing funders and institutions), the European University Association (institutions) and international discipline-specific bodies.

Reform of research assessment

Current evaluation criteria create perverse incentives that actively promote conventional publishing metrics. As a result, and perhaps unsurprisingly, research assessment reform emerged as the most powerful lever for change across all stakeholder groups; the range of ongoing initiatives in the space further corroborates this. Representatives from alternative publishing platforms noted how researchers express initial enthusiasm for their approaches but ultimately cannot justify the career risk of adoption when hiring, promotion and funding decisions remain tied to journal impact factors and publication counts.

Figure 3. An illustrative model to continue the transformation.

“It is often costly, especially for early career researchers, to not publish in somewhere that is recognisable, that has high impact factor that will allow them to progress in their career, because of how the incentive system is currently set up. And so it makes trying to publish with us almost risky.”

Alternative Publishing Platform

To see greater adoption of alternative publishing practices, assessment reform must move beyond aspirational statements toward concrete changes in evaluation criteria. This includes recognising preregistration, data sharing and reproducibility as markers of quality; valuing transparent peer review contributions; and explicitly crediting publications on alternative platforms.

Investment in infrastructure and capacity

The evidence points to a need for sustained public investment if more innovation in publishing practices is seen as a desirable outcome. The researchers we spoke to emphasised the need for investment to extend beyond technical systems to include human capacity: dedicated staff positions to support adoption, training for researchers in new practices and professional development for those implementing assessment reforms.

As noted above, innovation is essential to advance current practices and behaviours before they can be adopted at a larger scale. However, established infrastructure and publishing organisations may be less inclined to take on this role, as it involves considerable risks and may not align with their existing business models. Supporting platforms that explore new possibilities therefore requires recognising their role as research and development for the scholarly communication system: something that calls for collective public investment rather than reliance on competition.

Taking this forward in practice will require a mix of funding mechanisms (such as those explored in Section 3), with likely variation depending on national or regional policy landscapes.

Representation in digital infrastructure

Digital systems that track and index research outputs function as gatekeepers of legitimacy: if an output cannot be discovered, linked, cited or counted within these systems, many tend to de-prioritise it.

When alternative publishing practices lack this representation, researchers face a difficult choice: publish in ways that ‘count’ within existing systems, or adopt innovative practices that may be invisible to evaluators.

Achieving representation requires coordinated technical and policy work. Without these changes on digital infrastructures, even the most compelling alternative practices will struggle to achieve adoption, as researchers cannot afford to engage in scholarship that their key stakeholders cannot see.

Long-term implications

The transformation of scholarly communication requires recognising that innovation in publishing practices and platforms are not competing approaches but complementary strategies that must work in concert. The model outlined here acknowledges that meaningful change cannot be achieved through platform migration alone, nor can it succeed by expecting researchers to bear the career risks of early adoption without broader systemic support.

Delivering the benefits offered by alternative publishing depends on coordinated action across multiple levels of the research ecosystem:

- ▶ Systems and infrastructure (including indexes) must enable new practices with minimal friction.
- ▶ Disciplinary communities must normalise methodological rigour and transparency as core values.
- ▶ Funders and institutions must align their evaluation criteria and reward structures with the behaviours they claim to support.

The following opportunities (see Table 3) emerged from this investigation as priorities for stakeholders seeking to enable greater adoption of alternative publishing practices. These are not prescriptive requirements but

coordinated actions that, taken together, can create conditions where rigour, transparency and career advancement can align.

This transformation will not be rapid, but the growing acceptance of preprinting and open peer review in recent years demonstrates it is already underway.

The challenge now is to ensure that innovation in scholarly communication moves from the margins to the mainstream not by forcing impossible choices on researchers, but by creating the coordinated conditions outlined above, with multiple stakeholders acting simultaneously across levels to enable positive change.

Table 3. Opportunities for action to enable the adoption of alternative publishing practices.

Stakeholder group	Opportunities for action	Rationale from evidence
Research Funders (macro level)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Explicitly recognise outputs from alternative practices and platforms in assessment criteria ▶ Provide dedicated funding streams for experimentation with scholarly communication practices and platforms (not requiring commercial sustainability) ▶ Encourage or mandate open sharing practices (e.g., preprinting, open peer review) whilst permitting flexibility in venues 	Researchers adopt practices that align with career advancement; funder policies create legitimacy for non-conventional venues
Research Institutions (meso level)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Revise promotion and tenure criteria to value transparency, reproducibility and open practices ▶ Support researcher training and capacity building for new practices ▶ Invest in institutional infrastructure that enables alternative practices 	Assessment reform is the most powerful lever for change; researchers need both permission and capability to adopt innovations
Conventional Publishing Platforms (meso level)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Integrate proven alternative practices into existing workflows (e.g. open peer review, versioning, preprint integration) ▶ Adopt metadata schemas to describe emerging publication types 	Embedding innovations in mainstream infrastructure reduces adoption barriers; interoperability enables practice spread
Alternative Publishing Platforms (meso level)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Prioritise sustainability models that reduce reliance on volunteer labour ▶ Develop evidence of impact and value proposition ▶ Balance innovation with accessibility (reduce complexity where possible) 	Platform longevity builds researcher trust; demonstrated value enables funding arguments; usability affects adoption rates
Infrastructure Providers (indexes, Current Research Information Systems, repositories) (meso level)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Extend metadata schemas to represent new publication types ▶ Index and surface outputs from alternative platforms ▶ Enable linking and citation for non-conventional formats 	Invisibility in discovery systems is a fundamental adoption barrier; what cannot be found cannot be valued

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Appendix A: Acknowledgements and participants

Table A1: Knowledge exchange task and finish group on alternative publishing platforms

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Table A2: Project contributors

This table indicates the project contributors who consented for their information to be provided within the report. Two additional project contributors preferred not to be listed.

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